

EVALUATION AS A METHOD INSERTED IN BRAZILIAN EDUCATION FOR CLASSIFICATION-QUANTITATIVE PURPOSES

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ABSTRACT

In the timeline of educational historiography and assessment methods, it can be seen that education has gone through several phases. Time has brought the evolution of discoveries and the need for behavioral changes and, obviously, the need to lead society to develop new intellectual skills. Education has become an important tool to meet the demands of organizational structures, but amidst poverty and lack of investment in Brazilian education, there is a history based on low wages and precarious schools, and often hunger, poverty and sexual abuse are the villains in the teaching-learning process. Therefore, assessment methods only diagnose hunger and the lack of possibility of learning something, because no one learns anything on an empty stomach. The schooling process ceases to be a Jesuit universe and places itself at the feet of the Industrial Revolution, therefore the school began to need to improve assessment mechanisms and its assessment structure. Given this fact, assessment tools were intended to classify and select individuals. Within this context, it is observed that education and evaluation methods have always been, in a certain way, quantitative and have followed solid paths up to contemporary universal education.

Keywords: Poverty; Education; Evaluation; Traditionalism; Quantitative-classificatory method.

INTRODUCTION

This article aims to produce an analysis of the history of education and assessment and how the latter became a preponderant element of classification processes through exams applied to some social groups and, categorically, became an essential part of the learning process of contemporary Brazilian schools and of the entire educational process. The intention is to describe, in a brief and assertive way, the daily school life and the various difficulties encountered in the application of assessment methods, both in elementary school I (initial years) and elementary school II (final years).

Brazil has been promoting research to try to increase the scientific lines aimed at education through national master's and doctoral programs; but, even so, there are few programs and it seems that Brazilian education is not taking off. One gets the impression that research programs are unable [*or unwilling*] to come closer to school realities.

Brazilian researchers in the areas of human sciences, especially in the areas of Pedagogy and Didactics, should seek to interact with school communities and the daily life of these spaces, with the aim of reaching a broader and deeper understanding of what goes on inside schools; because those who do not know the reality of their people, their units and school communities are doomed to the difficulty, if not the impossibility, of developing in-depth and suitable research, connected with empirical reality. Therefore, researchers must develop a research format that communicates with the various spheres of the school floor, observing and analyzing the daily experiences that those involved go through and how they interpret, synthesize and respond to them.

The researcher cannot write his scientific work from his intellectual level, without knowing the empirical reality of the school environment, without understanding the national institutions or without realizing how the intrinsic relations of the respective global relations exert influences on individual and collective behaviors in the spaces of promotion of knowledge. Thus, the words of Morosini (2015) are cited, where he argues that,

The construction of a scientific production is related not only to the person/researcher who produces it, but to the influences of the institution in which he/she is inserted, the country in which he/she lives and his/her relations with the global perspective. In other words, the production is inserted in the scientific field and in its constitutive rules (Morosini, 2015, p. 02).

There are still few masters and doctors in the field of education who develop research capable of bringing about changes in educational thinking, especially because Brazil does not have the characteristics of producing innovative ideas, preferring to adopt them from the next priest who offers a miraculous cure for the evil that has always plagued the country's education system, which is the adoration of common sense explanations and the deadly aversion to those who possess elaborate scientific knowledge. To make this dire situation worse, the teachers who are on the production line and on the school floor do not have ongoing training appropriate to their real needs and do not have time to do research, reading or even plan their own classes.

Reflecting on the negative experiences that plague the lives of teaching professionals, we take the case of a literacy teacher who wakes up at 4 am to catch her bus, which is already crowded and she is very afraid of being robbed, once again; because she has already been

robbed several times. At the end of her workday, she returns home exhausted after a double or triple shift, goes to the bus stop and to get home, after enduring 3 (three) buses to get to her suburbs and still has a double shift for her own family.

It should be noted that many of these women still support their entire family circle with their teaching allowance; in many cases, their husbands are unemployed or they are separated. Through this tragic story, one can wonder how a teacher who earns little and who has so many difficulties in her private life still manages to have the psychological capacity to teach someone something?

The *establishment* knows that teachers are underpaid and that their personal lives are uncomfortable [*not to say miserable*]; however, it seems to be on purpose, always creating specific conditions for teachers to have difficulties; considering that a happy teacher would be more committed to encouraging students to learn. It seems that the system does not want a thinking population capable of developing appropriate political issues and choices.

It can be said that, since the 1960s, Brazil has increased its lines of research into education; however, only the elite are included in this universe. This information can be observed through the arguments of Morosini, Nascimento and Nez, who present the following contextualization in order to define this narrative:

The field of education occupies a space in the list of sciences, with emphasis on postgraduate studies. In Brazil, the development of postgraduate programs has been supported by public policies since the late 1960s, in a significant way. This translates into National Development Plans (PNDs), embodied in Science and Technology Development Plans (PDCTs) and Postgraduate Development Plans (PNPGs). This policy has been consolidated over time and the result, today, is 122,295 postgraduate students, of which 76,323 are academic masters, 4,008 professional masters and 41,964 doctorates. Specifically in the field of Education, there are 287 courses, of which 138 are academic masters, 94 doctorates, 52 professional masters and 3 professional doctorates. These courses are organized into 191 programs, 93 of which offer academic master's and doctorate degrees, 45 academic, 3 professional master's and doctorate degrees, and 49 professional (Morosini, Nascimento and Nez, 2021, p. 25).

Even though the number of researchers has increased, there is still a weakness in the teaching and learning process in national schools. This shows that the results of the research carried out have proven to be ineffective. It is clear that the school environment and the methodologies and assessment processes are the same as those used centuries ago. Within this context, it can be emphasized that times have changed, as have desires; however, schools continue to use the same quantitative-classifying methods.

The school has survived the years, the wars and the changes of seasons, of trends and philosophical thoughts applied to educational environments and systems; but it still establishes itself as the heir of a traditionalist and competitive culture; extremely exclusionary, which lives by making innocuous promises of social change and freedom. In fact, the individual who enters the literacy process or who learns a profession and, thus, establishes himself in the market as a professional who has managed to learn something for his own life and in favor of society can be considered as someone who has learned and who is free to learn more, as long as he so wishes.

Quantitative-classifying methods are still present in any educational space, and the test, as an evaluation method, is still suggested [*and, in a way, accepted*] as the only, most effective and fairest selection process capable of fairly evaluating students. This occurs because of the pragmaticity of such a method, the time savings it generates in applying the results and the efficiency in evaluating large groups of people at the same time. We cannot forget the extensive poverty spread throughout Brazil , where famine and drought ravage Brazilian families and children; therefore, education is lost amidst the suffering that materializes in the territory of misery and the lack of opportunities for those living in the circle of poverty and the hopelessness that it brings.

Therefore, a question must be raised in this text: who can learn anything when thirsty, hungry, afraid, or being a victim of external and internal aggression? Obviously, everyone already assumes the answer: no child can develop any skills with these items that are constantly and increasingly present in their existence. Therefore, hunger, poverty, thirst and fear in all forms prevent children from absorbing complex content that is equidistant from their reality. This narrative is present throughout Brazil and is still established today; however, it is argued that it is *only assumed* that all of this is a fact, because such contingent violence continues to happen and it seems that no one and no public agency takes any effective measures to end [*or at least mitigate*] this vicious cycle, which has already become a true moral and social aberration.

This story must have more negative aspects; because, to make matters worse, literacy teachers receive paltry subsidies, with which they are unable to alleviate their needs. It must also present the terrible conditions for teaching, because this lack of conditions and discouragement and consideration for the national teaching profession is part of our history of education in Brazil, where the knowledge of those who study is not valued and this generates an [*almost*] natural, phylogenetic feeling in the student of not being interested in what is being proposed by the teachers and the school itself; precisely because this child, who is unwary to

the point of being hopeless, knows the story of someone who *did not study and knows more than his teachers*.

We remember the lives of the sick, with teachers who threw themselves into carts or on the backs of donkeys, even when they were sick, to face the mud houses that served as schools in the rural area of the Northeast, surrounded by drought and infant mortality. This reality is the same throughout Brazil as a whole, and if you look around you will still find encounters of this nature, even in the 21st century. In the midst of so much suffering, there was a space where teachers worked for the love of their profession and for the pleasure of seeing a student identify the reading of his name and recognize the letters of his dignity and freedom imbued in the vowels and the alphabet.

Even in this territory of anguish, there are evaluation mechanisms to know whether or not the student has learned to write his or her own name and to read, decode, etc. Thus, the question arises whether subjective evaluation would be more efficient in perceiving the capabilities and cognitive abilities of students or whether the quantitative format would be fairer in a space where everyone is excluded, where students, teachers and the entire community live on the margins of the appreciation of life and existence with dignity.

Assessments still support the idea of selecting students through exams and measuring the cognitive and intellectual abilities of individuals in a cold, quantitative and classificatory way. If a student achieves a grade of 10, he is the best, and if the same student, on another occasion or in another subject, for some reason beyond his control, does not reach the required margin, he is doomed to despair and academic failure. There is no attempt to analyze the subjective conditions relevant to the student, considering that there is no time to do this procedure in assessments or in didactic-pedagogical tools.

The fact is that schools and education are not yet prepared for this mechanism, which requires adequate preparation on the part of teachers; quantitative resources and tests are still used as circumstantial resources in the training processes. Public examinations through quantitative tests are still and [*always*] will be the only way to evaluate individuals for approval in examinations and selection processes.

HISTORIOGRAPHICAL LINE OF EDUCATION AND EVALUATION: FROM ANTIQUITY TO THE PRESENT TIME

Before applying a non-chronological cut of events in the history of education and assessment, the proposal is to rekindle memories of the past and present without clinging

to specific dates; the aim is to show the various flaws in the Brazilian education system. In order to objectively highlight the weaknesses of education, initial fragments of the law that governs Brazilian education are shown here, which immediately presents a political desire; but which runs into deception; therefore, it begins by presenting data on Brazilian policy as set out in the LDB, which states:

TITLE II: Principles and Purposes of National Education Art. 2. Education, a duty of the family and the State, inspired by the principles of freedom and the ideals of human solidarity, has as its purpose the full development of the student, his preparation for the exercise of citizenship and his qualification for work. Art. 3. Education shall be provided based on the following principles: I - equality of conditions for access to and permanence in school; II - freedom to learn, teach, research and disseminate culture, thought, art and knowledge; III - pluralism of ideas and pedagogical concepts; IV - respect for freedom and appreciation of tolerance; V - coexistence of public and private educational institutions; VI - free public education in official establishments; VII - appreciation of the professional in school education; VIII - democratic management of public education, in accordance with this Law and the legislation of the educational systems; IX - guarantee of quality standards; X - appreciation of extra-curricular experience; XI - link between school education, work and social practices (Brazil, 2024, sp).

Even though Brazilian education has specifications centered on the National Curricular Guidelines for Early Childhood Education and even though assessment is also provided for in the National Education Plan (PNE) , there is still an educational model and an assessment process that only measures collective failure, in contrast to a few examples of success. This is because the Brazilian educational process has many flaws; there are school buildings with poor structure and a ridiculous minimum wage for the category. Obviously, these items contribute to a failure of education that extends to the assessment processes in everyday school life.

The curricular parameters must be followed; however, students do not have the capacity to follow what is provided for in the syllabus and descriptors. In the diagnostic assessment, it is already clear that students are not able to learn new content. Therefore, the diagnostic assessment period lasts for a long time, becoming a period of didactic leveling.

Right at the beginning, a diagnostic assessment is applied, which is often sent by the education department or the teachers themselves create their own assessments. The process has an immediate response, fraught with frustration for students and teachers, who realize that the students are lagging behind in their epistemology. And, amidst the pedagogical issues, there are spaces with poor conditions, rooms without the applicability

of images that contribute to the literacy process, hot rooms, uncomfortable chairs, and inadequate and misaligned lighting; an entire structural circle that negatively interferes with any learning process.

Therefore, in addition to the poor structures, there are teachers who work double or triple shifts and have difficult personal lives, who travel to school by bus or by car, always worried about their personal issues or car payments or the lack of money to fill up their vehicles. All these stresses in the daily lives of teachers contribute to creating a category with psychological problems.

It should be noted that there is a national policy that does not favor education professionals and does not understand that the Brazilian territory has a pluralized universe, culturally heterogeneous and marked by diverse problems. Historically, Brazil has been a land of illiterates who did not even have the right to vote. Therefore, see the specifications located at Agência Senado:

The illiterate would only cast their vote in November 1985, in the first election after the dictatorship, to choose mayors of capitals, hydromineral resorts and cities in national security areas. In these three decades, between the municipal elections of 1985 and those of last month, the total number of Brazilians unable to read and write fell from 19 million to 13 million - from 25% to 8% of the adult population (Agência Senado, 2024, sp)

For years, the Brazilian people did not have the right to vote or to learn to read and write; as a result, the nation's history is made up of families who never had access to basic education. This debt that Brazil has with our people has left a cursed legacy of entire families who had their lives destroyed. family tree composed with a history of sadness and academic ignorance. History shows us that ancestors have a family that was never included in literacy and lacked freedom and understanding of constitutional or biblical narratives, as the people did not know how to read or write.

The term literacy is a new expression within the educational context, in which Literacy is a word that has recently arrived in the vocabulary of Education and Linguistic Sciences: it is in the second half of the 1980s that it appears in the discourse of specialists in these areas. One of the first occurrences is in a book by Mary Kato, from 1986 (*No mundo da escrita: uma perspectiva psicolinguística*, Editora Ática): the author, right at the beginning of the book (p.7), says that she believes that the standard spoken language "is a consequence of literacy" (my emphasis). Two years later, in a book from 1988 (*Adultos não alfabetizados: o avesso do avesso*, Editora Pontes), Leda Verdiani Tfouni, in the introductory chapter,

distinguishes literacy from literacy: perhaps this is the moment when literacy gains the status of a technical term in the lexicon of the fields of Education and Linguistic Sciences.

Since then, the word has become increasingly frequent in the written and spoken discourse of specialists, to the point that, in 1995, it was already included in the title of a book organized by Ângela Kleiman: *The meanings of literacy: a new perspective on the social practice of writing* (emphasis added, see reference in note 1). What explains the recent emergence of this word? New words are created (or old words are given a new meaning) when new facts, new ideas, new ways of understanding phenomena emerge. What new fact, or new idea, or new way of understanding the presence of writing in the social world brought about the need for this new word, *fetramento*?

If the word literacy still seems strange to many, other words in the same semantic field have always been familiar to us: illiteracy, illiterate, alphabetizing, alphabetization, literate and even literate and illiterate. Illiteracy, as defined by the New Aurélio Dictionary of the Portuguese Language, is *the state or condition of being illiterate*, and illiterate is *someone who cannot read and write*, that is, someone who lives in the state or condition of someone who cannot read and write; the action of teaching literacy, that is, according to Aurélio, of *teaching how to read* (and also how to write, which the dictionary curiously omits) is called literacy, and literate is *someone who knows how to read* (and write). According to the same dictionary, literate is someone *versed in letters, erudite*, and illiterate is *someone who has no literary knowledge* and also the *illiterate or almost illiterate*. The Aurélio dictionary does not record the word *literacy*. This word appears, however, in a dictionary of the Portuguese language published over a century ago, the Dictionary of the Contemporary Portuguese Language, by Caldas Aulete: in its 3rd Brazilian edition.

This map of the illiterate, or, as you prefer, the word illiteracy, has spread throughout the modern history of national education. Thus, to define the terminology literacy with more emphasis, we still argue based on the thinking of Soares (2008) who presents the concept of literacy. Therefore, we cite here what she expresses as literacy:

literacy 'literally'. *Letre-*, from the Latin *littera*, and the suffix *-mento*, which denotes the result of an action (as, for example, in wounding, the result of the action of wounding). Literacy is, therefore, the result of the action of teaching or learning to read and write: the state or condition acquired by a social group or an individual as a consequence of having appropriated writing (Soares, 2008, p. 68).

Brazil is still experiencing a period of illiteracy pandemic that does not allow freedom for the people. Years have passed and the numbers have been decreasing, but at a

very slow pace. There is still a significant contingent of illiterate citizens spread throughout the country. The national literacy process has begun to undergo important transformations; even so, there are serious problems, because even though society is being involved in the learning process, the interpretation process is stalled in other instances, because even if the individual manages to know the letters and vowels and write short readings and short texts or medium or long texts, they still live immersed in a nation marked and dominated by functional illiteracy and little participation in the field of reading and writing.

This way,

As illiteracy is overcome, as an increasing number of people learn to read and write, and as, concomitantly, society becomes increasingly centered on writing (increasingly graphocentric), a new phenomenon becomes evident: it is not enough to simply learn to read and write. People become literate, learn to read and write, but they do not necessarily incorporate the practice of reading and writing, nor do they necessarily acquire the ability to use reading and writing, to engage in social writing practices: they do not read books, newspapers, magazines, do not know how to write a letter, a request, a statement, do not know how to fill out a form, have difficulty writing a simple telegram, a letter, cannot find information in a telephone directory, an employment contract, an electricity bill, a medicine leaflet... This new phenomenon only gains visibility after the problem of illiteracy has been minimally resolved and social, cultural, economic and political development brings new, intense and varied reading and writing practices, giving rise to new needs, as well as new leisure alternatives. As the new phenomenon emerged, it was necessary to give it a name: when a new word appears in the language, it is because a new phenomenon has emerged and had to be named. Therefore, and to name this new phenomenon, the word literacy emerged (SOARES, 2009, p. 12).

Returning to the map of the evaluation process in Brazil, it is clear that the understanding of the evaluation method as an educational resource is a historically recent terminology. It should be noted that in Brazil, the contextualization and discussions about evaluation methods are only 40 (forty) years old. There are only 4 (four) decades in which researchers have approached the subject scientifically. During this period of almost half a century, few things have changed in the educational spheres. Thus, we can mention here an idea by Luckesi, raised in the book *Avaliação da aprendizagem escolar estudos e proposições (Evaluation of school learning: studies and propositions)* (2011). This book helps to reflect on the subject with the following reflection:

In the case of Brazil, we began to talk about learning assessment in the late 1960s and early 1970s of the 20th century, so we have been dealing with this topic and this school practice for around forty years. Before, we only talked about school exams. The LDB, from 1961, still contains a chapter on school exams and Law No. 5.692/71, which redefined the education system in the

country in 1971, stopped using the expression 'school exams' and started using the expression 'measurement of school performance', but it has not yet used the term 'learning assessment'. Only the LDB, from 1996, used this expression in the legislative body (Luckesi, 2011, p. 29).

Throughout history, the terminology of educational policy has changed its names, but the process in everyday school life remains the same. The change from the terminology of *exam* to *assessment* has not been very successful, as schools still use the formatting of the usability of exams in everyday school life and in university settings. Still dialoguing with Luckesi, he argues that,

In this case, our current educational legislation has managed to assimilate the new proposals, but our school practice is still far from achieving this. In our schools, both public and private, as well as in our various levels of education, we practice many more school exams than learning assessments. Hence, the formulation of the title of my lecture, although it surprised me, seemed to me to be deeply significant. We need to “learn to assess”, because we are still examining more than assessing. Our common sense, in school life, is that of examiners and not evaluators (Idem, 2011, p. 29).

According to the aforementioned author, examination methods were introduced into educational history in the 16th and 17th centuries, when the beginning of globalization and the technological and industrial revolution gave rise to a certain emergency to meet modernity and its new nuances.

The resources used by educational school exams in Brazilian territory as established in contemporary education models are a tool of the educational legacy left by the Jesuit educational process and, even though there is a changeability in the timeline of secular historiography, the process gained stability in national education under different formats; however, the method is still the same, consolidating itself as a methodology for the process of evaluating credibility and classification throughout human history, leading the practice of traditional education of the exam to establish itself and become naturalized in the process of teaching and monitoring formal learning.

The evaluation process within Brazilian schools or academic institutions is directed towards the quantitative path and the guidelines for constructing the test as the only classification resource. Some authors claim that the test has practically become something of a fetish in its applicability and in its preparation. Thus, it is interesting to quote the words of Luckesi (2010), where he highlights that,

Throughout the history of modern education and our educational practice, the assessment of school learning, through exams and tests, has become a fetish. By fetish we understand an "entity" created by human beings to meet a need,

but which becomes independent of them and dominates them, becoming universal (Luckesi, 2010, p. 69).

Before looking back on the path of education and the assessment process, we continue to discuss Luckesi (2010), who analyzes education and assessment methods as a dictatorial and authoritarian context that does not allow for any other possibility of assessing students in the academic world. Therefore, the author's argument is as follows:

We have already had the opportunity to mention and give some treatment to the topic of the present discussion, which deals with the issue of authoritarianism in the practice of school educational assessment and its possible overcoming through intra-school means (Luckesi, 1984a and 1984b). On this occasion, however, we intend to organize and systematize, in a more organic and appropriate way, this analysis and subsequent proposal of a way of acting that may represent an advance beyond the limits within which the practice of educational assessment in the classroom is currently demarcated (Luckesi, 2010, 78).

In the history of humanity, man has always been seen as learning some skill for his survival. Since the caveman, the human species has been developing new skills, such as building the wheel and perceiving the importance and danger of fire; discoveries that changed the power of primitive man and brought about the beginning of his evolution.

At other times in history, it is noted that man has always been involved in the process of developing new tools and skills that were responsible for consolidating his evolution as a species. In this way, the history of humanity reveals that the process of mutability of knowledge has never been stagnant and, with each change in the process, new ways of evaluating it were needed.

There have been several periods that have changed human behavior in a positive or negative way. One example is the Industrial Revolution, which had a profound impact on the behavior of the European population and led to changes in the habits of many peoples around the world. Social groups had different educational lives and customs before the revolution; with the new machines, society needed to learn how to educate itself in order to develop new cognitive skills and break away from the medieval, predominantly agricultural period.

During this period of the industrial revolution, the school environment began to undergo changes and the process began to become competitive, as it was necessary to meet the demands of the organizational world and the industrial revolution that was sweeping Europe; but, obviously, the educational process changed slowly. Reinforcing what was specified above, it is clear that the teaching and learning process has always been inserted into human assessments

and methods for selecting people. Therefore, with the evolution of the human species, the process of cognitive development allowed individuals to achieve new learning possibilities.

Time passed and the human species or some great personalities began to realize that we needed to evolve through science and technology. The world changed with new discoveries and the school still remains stagnant, using the same evaluation mechanisms or with its traditionalist tools in everyday educational life.

The process has been the same for decades and it seems that very slowly there is a light at the bottom of the well in the process of change in schooling and student assessment. It should be remembered that education has always been present in the history of the human race. Primitive man developed his educational methods, driving his groups to survival. At another time in humanity, engravings and stories were used as teaching resources. Throughout the historiography of humanity and in the space of life, the process of learning is being learned in some way; because this mechanism leads to freedom.

As a figurative example, we can take the physicist-chemist Oppenheimer (1904-1967), who seized and created the atomic bomb; he was responsible for the invention of the bomb that would kill hundreds of people and would go down in the history of humanity as *a murderous genius*. This milestone in the history of humanity brought great reflection to the world with the discovery of the great vehicle that was marked as the promise of death. This genius of chemistry and physics developed his intellectual abilities through traditionalist educational mechanisms and quantitative assessment methods; therefore, are the methods mentioned above really outdated and can qualitative methods be used to lead the student to develop their abilities or is all this nothing more than a farce and, really, is the traditional test the only means of assessing the student in a cold and pragmatic way?

Entering another sphere of human history, it is worth noting that assessment methods have always been present in the context of the human species. It can be said that, in some tribes, the youngest who were in the learning process went through the assessment method through their cultural customs, the so-called rites of passage. Several civilizations spread across the planet, throughout history, have had the method of examinations in their routine to obtain positions of power or sociocultural prestige. Given this fact, it is worth emphasizing again that, throughout human history, there have always been times when the assessment process was present in some way.

Following a disoriented and chronological path, it is shown that the history of modern education shows that the schooling process has always been traditionalist, labor-based, and classificatory. Thus, the contemporary school is the result of a dictatorial and religious ideology.

In the medieval period, schooling was maintained in monasteries and few had the privilege of being included in this academic life.

In the midst of this religious academic elitism, there was a predominantly masculinized educational universe. In the space for promoting intellectuality, the evaluation method was traditionalist and with the presence of a great religious intellectual who placed himself in the superior position of evaluator.

Taking a circumstantial leap from historical times, we arrive at the Brazilian colonialist sphere. In Brazilian territory, the schooling process began with the arrival of the Jesuits in their caravels with the aim of catechizing the Brazilian indigenous community that had been culturally, economically and sexually plundered. With the presence of the priests, the first schools were born that had as a model traditionalism that places the priest as a central figure in stages of traditional education.

With the presence of Dom Pedro residing in Brazil the educational process changed, because,

With the presence of D. João VI in Brazil for more than a decade, changes were seen in the framework of educational institutions of the time, with the creation of non-theological higher education: Royal Navy Academy, Royal Military Academy, medical-surgical courses, the presence of the French Cultural Mission, the creation of the Botanical Garden, the Royal Museum, the Public Library and the Royal Press. Relevant for being the first centers of education and culture in Brazil, they reveal the aristocratic intentions of D. João, since primary education was forgotten and the population in general remained illiterate and without access to the great centers of knowledge. During the Monarchy, high value was given to higher education. This reflects the need for qualified personnel to fill the administrative staff of the country that had recently become politically free (Marçal Ribeiro, 1993, p. 27).

It is worth remembering that when the Europeans arrived in Brazil, the indigenous people lived by preserving their values and their lands and did not need any help to survive, as they had nature on their side, knowledge of it and control over it. The sociocultural impact was devastating and slowly destroyed the values of the indigenous communities. Years passed and the Brazilian lands were colonized and the process of cultural mixing spread throughout the territory.

History did not stand still and the Portuguese brought their schools to Brazil, following the times of history and records and the Brazilian educational process was consolidated, leading to literacy for an entire population that was not literate according to the stereotypes of the European people and the Jesuits.

It can be said that the educational process in Brazilian territory became official in 1930, when the *Ministry of Education and Public Health* was created, responsible for creating educational policies and developing matters related to teaching and public health.

With this interference, the evaluation method became a crucial governmental and organizational tool, leading schools to adopt this rule. As is well known, the entire educational process was built on models promoted by ancestors and which are still present today. As a result, the evaluation process that is prevalent in schools continues to be the quantitative method, or rather, the famous tests full of tricks that were often designed to fail students and not to teach them through them.

Brazil is a country with continental dimensions, frightening distances and for years it was unable to teach its people to read and write, which left a mark on its history of exclusion and lack of freedom for a people who left behind a lack of life expectancy. The Brazilian political class thought it was favorable for the population not to know how to interpret things in life or at school, because intelligent people are people who work hard and recognize their natural and political rights.

It should be remembered that Brazil had a time when teachers had no academic training and worked with few pedagogical resources; they faced distances in rural areas in territories dominated by hunger and poverty, and in the dry northeast without basic conditions to teach the *basics* to illiterate and malnourished children who lived only on divine permission. Small schools, with architecture made of clay and wood. The teachers, with their low salaries, had no support from anyone or anything.

This story followed a fortified path and Brazilian education is reduced to an international embarrassment that is always present in the political platforms of those running for political office. Within this context, the education agenda is always present in electoral campaigns that continue to this day, when teachers still fight for their rights and end up losing their strength.

The demonstrations and strikes of the category lead teachers to stop in the streets to fight for their rights and are attacked with rubber bullets and tear gas. Therefore, here is an excerpt from an article that talks about the demonstration of teachers in the state of Espírito Santo on 03/17/2014, published in the newspaper G1-ES, with information from TV Gazeta and Rádio CBN Vitória:

Two groups of teachers from the municipal schools in Serra and Vila Velha, in Espírito Santo, held demonstrations and caused traffic to slow down in Greater Vitória on Monday morning (17). According to the Federal Highway Police (PRF), part of the BR-101 highway in Carapina, in Serra, was closed and a traffic jam formed. Teachers from Serra were dispersed by the PRF using tear gas and pepper

spray. According to the agency, the police did not overdo it. According to the police, the protest should have been warned and the measure was taken by the officers after the total closure in both directions of Reta do Aeroporto, near the radar. The Serra city government reported that it is talking to the teachers. The administration announced a 6% salary increase for all employees, including education professionals, and a 20% increase in food vouchers. According to the city government, this is the maximum possible to respect the limit established by law for spending on personnel. The city government of Vila Velha reported that teachers in the municipality received an 8% increase starting this month of March and said that it is developing policies to value the category. The teachers are following the national program suggested by the National Confederation of Education Workers (CNTE), which demands compliance with the law on minimum wage, career and working hours, investment of oil royalties in the valorization of the category, immediate voting of the National Education Plan and 10% of the GDP for public education. In addition, the teachers are against the governors' proposal to readjust the minimum wage (A GAZETA, 2014, SP).

Demonstrations and strikes are common throughout Brazil, because minimum wages are low and teachers are unable to live with dignity. In the past, teachers who taught in rural areas did all their homework at school. They were often responsible for providing lunch for the children who went to school to eat. In the midst of suffering and despair, teachers tried to encourage students to develop new skills or become literate. Hunger, thirst and poverty were enemies of the learning process, because no one learns anything when they are hungry.

On several occasions, the teacher would teach several classes and divide the board in half to assign the activities. With such a lack of support, the teachers still had the will to create assessment activities that were of no use. Years passed, the school was remodeled with computers and quality food; however, the students' lack of interest became very large and the teachers' allowance continues to be humiliating. This lack of appreciation for teaching and the lack of student encouragement lead teachers to lose the desire to teach, leading many of them to become ill. Thus, we experience a pandemic of anxiety and stress that is part of the daily lives of education workers.

Some professions are part of the catalogue of daily suffering, such as police officers, health professionals and teachers, who are victims of political neglect and the lack of a salary plan. The teaching profession is seen by the International Labour Organization (ILO) as an area of activity with the highest rate of stressful actions, with a high incidence of elements that lead to *Burnout Syndrome*. This phenomenon, which affects education professionals in different countries, seems to have an international epidemic character that goes beyond national borders (Gil-Monte, 2008).

Teachers experience a daily life marked by violence and neglect, thus contributing to a diagnosis of fear and real psychological problems. In addition to the notorious violence, the

lack of appreciation, resources or appropriate conditions also contributes to teachers becoming ill. This, for example, is related to several possibilities linked not only to the infrastructure of the school environment, but also to low salaries, stressful and excessive workdays and even the number of students per classroom.

The teaching profession has been perceived since the beginning of scientific studies on Burnout Syndrome (BS) as one of the most investigated. In the late seventies, more specifically, in 1979, there was already the first record of a descriptive scientific study directed and carried out with teachers (Perlman & Hartman, 1982).

In the 1980s, interest in Burnout grew, as several studies showed results that were considered dangerous and alarming in relation to teachers. Obviously, this whole situation influences the work of teachers and, consequently, influences the learning process of students. It is important to mention that some students go to school with other obscure objectives that are not part of the pedagogical curriculum. Thus, fear, on many occasions, is perpetuated in the lives of education professionals, as some do not have a car and wake up early to catch the bus and walk a long way to get to school.

Along the way, they are mugged, lose their cell phones and all their dignity. All of these negative events disrupt school life and lead to pedagogical failure and, obviously, to failure in the various assessments that are carried out to diagnose the students' abilities. Currently, some students do not respect pedagogical life, nor the teachers or anyone who is part of the school's pedagogical team, and if the caning method were to return, teachers would probably be prosecuted or arrested for violence, if not they would be subjected to it.

Years have passed, times have changed, desires have changed, life stories have changed; but the school routine remains rooted in the same evaluation method. Obviously, the teacher's power has been lost; but education remains the same, without hope.

In Brazilian scientific literature, there are authors who say that the teaching and learning process needs to have a direct relationship with the individual's daily life, for example, if the student works as a bricklayer, methods that remind him of his professional universe should be used. Paulo Freire (1921-1997) was an author who believed that learning should start from the students' reality, valuing the universe of practice and guiding them to develop a critical reading of the world.

It should be mentioned here that the literacy process has been the same for decades; therefore, can it be said that traditional resources in the construction of the literacy journey are still effective today? Currently, technology is a contributing resource to help in the teaching and learning process and in the way of teaching a child to read and write; however, it seems

that the traditional method is still functional and that it, in fact, contributes to the literacy of hundreds of students.

Today, it is often said that traditional educational tools are still fundamental in pedagogical life and that technology only contributes to the desired path. Many experts claim that the word tool refers us to the technical philosophy of education and that the process should not bring back memories of a technical era, in which subjects should be considered automatons to help in the economy and in the organizational world.

In contemporary schools, the intention is to have a respectful path for education; at least that is what the authorities say, or is it just rhetoric? Apparently, there is a movement to revitalize the educational process and assessment methods in the daily lives of students and teachers; but there are still the remains of old-fashioned education, which are still embedded in practice and will not be removed from Brazilian curricula any time soon, since all the people were taught to read and write in this way; therefore, the old method must be respected.

There is still everywhere the quantitative mechanism or objective or discursive test to evaluate students or any person being evaluated. There are several mandatory tests in Brazilian schools that are classificatory, such as the Basic Education Assessment System (SAEB) test, which every year brings a sad mapping of students with limited capacity to interpret short texts or develop small textual productions.

In the state of Espírito Santo, the PAEBES is applied every year, measuring students' productivity capacity or incapacity. This is a negative map of the regional school system. For years, the entrance exam was the only way to enter higher education; currently, there are other ways to enter college; however, there are also students with severe functional illiteracy who are unable to interpret short texts. To make matters worse, many projects are done in groups, preventing students from producing everything on their own.

We are not here to demonize tests or quantitative methods; however, tests should not be the only mechanism for evaluating or condemning people. Tests have become a cold and calculating format that does not allow the process to see the student in a comprehensive way. The test mechanism sentences students in a cruel way; sometimes they are condemned by the test with a lower grade, because the test was constructed through the teacher's fetish with the objective of eliminating the student. Following this line of thought, the following argument is used:

The grade, mark, and concept are given to the student without interpretation or questioning as to their meaning and power. These periodic, terminal sentences hinder the understanding of constructive error and its dimension in

the search for truths in schools. They prevent teachers and students from establishing a relationship of interaction based on joint reflection and questioning of hypotheses formulated by the student in his or her discovery of the world. This also results in a relationship of antagonism (teacher and student) that leads to painful episodes of evaluation. Irrevocable sentences. Inflexible judges. Defendants, for the most part, are guilty. The teacher painfully fulfills a bureaucratic requirement, and the student, in turn, suffers the evaluation process. At this moment, both lose and decharacterize the evaluation of its basic meaning of investigation and dynamization of the knowledge process (Hoffman, 2011, pp. 17 and 18).

It should be understood that sometimes the student knows the content and can contextualize the ideas; however, due to some situation of stress, fear, insecurity, health problem or trauma, the student is unable to do well on a test. Thus, it is stated that the test, therefore, should be interpreted as a guiding vehicle to contribute to the learning process and not a condemning or classificatory resource, and should be an instrumental method that contributes to the process of verification of the teachers' monitoring and an auxiliary path that can be inserted as support for the complementary subjective format.

The test must be understood as a complementary instrument for students' skills and as part of an integrated universe for assessing learning, in order to promote greater equality among students through the guideline of monitoring students' learning and reviewing the teacher's methodology and teaching methods.

, Veiga (2012) is quoted , where he states that,

Assessment only makes sense in the broad process of education when it is thought out, planned and executed with the aim of helping these people, whether they are teachers and/or students, to learn more and better, to reorient their paths, their ways of studying and dealing with knowledge, clarifying and presenting the weaknesses and potential of each one in relation to a certain type of knowledge (VEIGA, 2012, p. 147).

It should be noted that the main types of assessment are *diagnostic assessment* , which seeks to identify what the student already knows; *formative assessment* , which aims at training, that is, learning; and *summative assessment* , which aims to assign grades to demonstrate whether the learning goal has been achieved. Daily school life is a topic that is always being assessed and contextualized.

The assessment process is very complex and can lead to injustice, as the test cannot be the only extremely important resource for assessing or judging a student's ability. Often, students end up doing well on tests, but in reality they are unable to develop actions and skills compatible with the knowledge memorized and exemplified in the tests.

How many times does a student fail a test? He knows the content of the test, but the format of the assessment leads him to make mistakes and to fail the classification; in this way, we must remember Libâneo's narratives:

Assessment is a complex task that is not limited to carrying out tests and assigning grades. Measurement only provides data that must be subjected to a qualitative assessment. Assessment, therefore, fulfills pedagogical-didactic, diagnostic and control functions in relation to which instruments are used to verify academic performance (Libâneo, 2013, p. 216).

It is not intended here to present statistical spreadsheets with updated data on the map of Brazilian educational failure; rather, it is emphasized that, currently, in Brazilian territory there are statistical data that create a real embarrassment for the country, as the records show that a frightening number of students completing elementary school I are still not literate or do not know how to do simple math.

This educational failure extends to all stages of the student's life, who is unable to interpret short texts or produce small textual productions; therefore, we have a Brazil where the map of functional illiteracy is consecrated even among higher education students. Vieira argues that,

Assessment is the measurement between the teacher's teaching and the teacher's and student's learning; it is the thread of communication between the ways of teaching and the ways of learning. It is necessary to consider that students learn differently because they have different life stories, they are historical subjects, and this conditions their relationship with the world and influences their way of learning. Assessment, then, is also seeking information about the student (their life, their community, their family, their dreams...) it is getting to know the subject and their way of learning (Freire, 1996; Malheiros; Amaral, 2013, p. 219).

The evaluation process within the school is guided by the traditionalist system and by families who still believe that a good teacher is one who teaches a lot of material on the board and makes the students' hands go numb from copying so much. Many times, the students don't even know what they are copying and sometimes not even the teacher knows what he or she is writing on the board. When a teacher does a dynamic activity or tries to create a different class and the students don't copy anything from the board, they come home and say that the teacher didn't teach anything important and was just messing around the whole time. Automatically, the family complains that the teacher is not working properly.

Within this bias of erroneous perception of the family, it is noted that the actions of the school's functionality clash with society's ignorance. The climate of tension and the demand to get a good grade or copy everything from the board is combined with the family's concern about

whether the student has a passing grade or if he obtained the grade necessary to advance to the next year, even if he has not developed any cognitive and/or intellectual, subjective or quantitative skills.

The family's greatest concern is not whether the student has actually learned anything; but whether he has progressed to the next grade; therefore, the students' loved ones or parents, relatives and teachers are also apprehensive about this issue. As Luckesi (2010) points out,

Parents are eager for their children to advance in the school grades; teachers constantly use assessment procedures as a means of motivating students, through threats; students are always expecting to pass or fail, and to do so, they use a variety of expedients (Luckesi, 2010, p. 18).

Currently, school environments do not use failure as a punitive resource or to recognize that the student is not prepared to advance to the next grade; therefore, when they reach the next grade, they are unable to learn or grasp the content, as they do not have sufficient cognitive capacity to be inserted into the new reality.

Finally, the assessment process in schools is still quantitative and the system supports this methodological assessment resource. Even if there is a full-time school where the student spends practically the entire day inside the school, there are still spaces that are not suitable for studying and the educational process remains the same. We know that changes are needed; however, we are still stuck in the old patterns and it is unlikely that there will be a positive change or improvement in education in the short term; the future of education is uncertain and is hindered by the failure of the school.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The Brazilian educational system, given its federative dimension, in which all decisions are unanimous for the entire national territory, disregarding its particularities and singularities, ends up producing, as a consequence of its centralized form of administration, an evaluation mechanism in which the State holds maximum control, even managing to optimize the correction processes and responses to users.

In addition to the above, the force introduced into the schooling process and the educational heritage are very strong in Brazilian curricular guidelines and in the evaluation process. With the changes in the State structures, there is a need for the principles of identity, diversity and autonomy to be redefined in favor of the relationship to be maintained between the education systems and the schools. It is important to emphasize that this proposal should

not be understood as an absence or omission of the State. On the contrary, the identity and autonomy of schools are exercised in the context constituted by general guidelines for action and advice on the implementation of educational policies, which requires effective participation of the educational systems (federal, state or municipal), so that autonomy does not become neglect or abandonment.

This gives rise to the need to define guidelines within an educational policy that reflects the needs and demands of the system, in line with the National Guidelines and the structuring of efficient and effective mechanisms for supervision, advice, monitoring and evaluation of the results of schools' performance. It ends up being complex to judge the Brazilian evaluation system as good or bad, fair or unfair, because if the quantitative-classificatory model is eliminated, for another mode in which there is a form of judgment based on quantitative analyses, it would not be possible to meet the demand in a timely manner, due to the contingent of individuals who participate in the processes.

In particular situations, in the classroom, the teacher can even use assessment strategies in which students are assessed based on and according to their pressing potential; however, this is yet another utopia that leads many professionals to get lost in trying to achieve them, without success, precisely because they meet a very extensive demand from students.

The most that can be sought to apply is a mechanism for preparing the assessment in which it explores, as deeply as possible, the creativity, intelligence, skills, capacity for analysis, interpretation and synthesis of the students and, with this, obtains a response that is as objective as possible regarding the object and knowledge that is intended to be submitted for assessment.

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